

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

DOI

ISSN 2181-2357

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ Nashriyot markazi.

A. M. Abdullayev

1-tom, 1-son.

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

Noyabr 2021 y.

2021 yil noyabr oyidan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi.

16+

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, FarPI rektori

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, A.A.Shermukhamedovsh, Y.S.A. H.A.Akramov, M.X.Hakimov, Sh.M.Iskandarova, Z.M.Sobirova, A.M.Muxtorova, L.M.Babaxo'jaeva.

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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 4446-5760-5988-7507-e628-4252-5710 2021 yil 23 mart.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

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Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.
Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2021. T. 1. №1. <https://alferganus.uz>

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2021 Farg'ona, O'zbekiston
ISSN 2181-2357

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DOI

Publishing Center «Al-Ferganus» LLC.

A. M. Abdullaev

“International journal of theoretical and practical research”

Scientific Journal.

2021.

Published since November 2021.

Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 1, Issue 1

November,

Chairman of the Editorial Board Salomov Uktam Rakhimovich, Rector of FerPI

Editor-in-chief K. I. Kurpayanidi

Editorial Board: A. M. Abdullaev, M. S. Ashurov, E. A. Muminova, K. Kh. Abdurakhmanov, A. N. Asaul, A. V. Burkov, U. V. Gafurov, M. A. Ikramov, D. Kudbiev, E. S. Margianiti, B. Obrenovich, L. Ivars, K. E. Onarkulov, N. A. Sultanov, A. Khasanov, Sh. T. Karimov, Sh. Sh. Khamdamova, D. S. Salikhanova, U.K. Alimov, S.M. Turabdzhonov, B.A.Alimatov, R.Zh. Tozhiev, A.A. Riskulov, B.M. Tursunov, A.A. Shermukhamedov, S. F. Ergashev, Y.S. Abbasov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.Kh. Khakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Mukhtarova, L.M. Babakhodzhaeva.

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Phone +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

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Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Registration No. 4446-5760-5988-7507-e628-4252-5710 dated March 23, 2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2021). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 1(1).

<https://alferganus.uz>

© Publishing Center«Al-Ferganus»,
2021, Fergana, Uzbekistan
ISSN 2181-2357

Издательский центр «Al-Ferganus» ООО.

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

DOI

А. М. Абдуллаев

Том 1, Номер 1.

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Ноябрь 2021г.

Издается с ноября 2021г.

Выходит один раз в месяц.

16+

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, Ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

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Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 4446-5760-5988-7507-е628-4252-5710 от 23 марта 2021 года.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2021. Т. 1.
№1. <https://alferganus.uz>

©Издательский центр «Al-Ferganus»,
2021 Фергана, Узбекистан

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DOI

International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2021 Issue: 1

Volume: 1

Published:

01.11.2021

<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Khodjaeva, N. A., Jumanova, A.B. (2021). Management and its components in tourism industry of Uzbekistan. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 1 (1),44-49.

Doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5731479>

QR-Article

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MANAGEMENT AND ITS COMPONENTS IN TOURISM INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract: *For individual, tourism is a popular leisure activity. for a city/county tourism has become economy driver. The objective of this paper is to discuss management and its components in tourism activity in Uzbekistan, as these elements affect competitiveness of tourism organizations.*

Keywords: *tourism, management of tourism industry, elements of tourism products.*

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МЕНЕДЖМЕНТ И ЕГО СОСТАВЛЯЮЩИЕ В ИНДУСТРИИ ТУРИЗМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация: *Для индивида туризм является популярным видом досуга. для города/округа туризм стал драйвером экономики. Целью данной статьи*

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является обсуждение менеджмента и его составляющих в туристической деятельности в Узбекистане, поскольку эти элементы влияют на конкурентоспособность туристических организаций.

Ключевые слова: туризм, управление туристической отраслью, элементы туристических продуктов.

Introduction

Many countries depend on tourism as economy driver. Tourism can be domestic or international. International tourism has both incoming and outgoing implications on a country's balance of payments. The concern generally related to increase revenue from tourism. To be successful on tourism business someone should concern with management. As for individual, tourism is a leisure activity, management should work for tourists experience. This paper was intended to discuss tourism management in Uzbekistan.

Discussion

Tourism as a control object has a number of which are features inherent only to it that are largely due to the specifics of the industry. The task of management is to detect such features in the future to include them in the management of tourism enterprises and organizations. The first feature of tourism in terms of management is a large scale of tourism industry and the complexity of the relationships between its components. The second feature of tourism as an object of control can be considered conflicting and complex definition of objectives of administrative influence. At first glance it may seem that private tourism enterprises targets are clear enough, they are accumulation values, profit earning. However, travel companies often guided by the statement, and not on the actual needs of tourists. To reveal the least, a manager must endeavor, as ineffectiveness of his activities may provoke dissatisfaction of a consumer. It is rather difficult to define clear objectives and criteria for tourist organizations of national, regional, local (city, district) levels, which hampers an objective assessment of their contribution to the development of tourism, forecast and planning activities of such organizations. More complex is a development of individual tourist areas, regions. It is not easy to accurately predict all phenomena and processes occurring in tourism (the changes in the political situation, deteriorating weather conditions, changes in the tax system, etc.), so they often can speak only about the probabilistic nature of forecasts and plans. Thus, tourism is a phenomenon that is difficult to predict and measure. One of the most important features of tourism as a control object is specificity of tourism services and tourism product. They must be considered when designing the system management of tourism enterprises, organizations and territories, in establishing service standards, staff training, etc. Specific requirements for the management district tourism bring and specificity of

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tourist demand, which has a heterogeneous character and stands out among other reasons:

- intangibility and preservation of tourism products;
- diversity of consumer preferences;
- high importance of social factors.

On the management of tourism sector, and this affects its feature as a service in the complex during the stay of tourists on holiday. It is this complex is the basis of the tourist demand. Depending on the customers to the forefront can leave this or that service. Tourism products created by the efforts of many organizations are independent of each other. As a result, it increases the value of cooperation both horizontally and vertically, which facilitates services fall in the complex. Under the influence of a number of objective and subjective factors: climatic, economic, social (free time), demographic, psychological (traditions, fashion), logistical (the development of a network of institutions of accommodation, food, transport, etc.). There formed seasonality of tourism supply and demand. All of these factors, especially climatic conditions determine seasonal fluctuations in demand for tourist services. Their accounting must be the manager of travel agencies to develop a proposal and take action to reduce unevenness in demand for tourist services. Another feature of tourism is the fact that its development affects a much larger number of stakeholders than in any other human activity. Wednesday tourist activity includes customers, suppliers' companies, manufacturers of individual tourist and non-touristic services rulers bodies and agencies, local authorities, social funds, public and other organizations, etc., which affect or may affect it. Tourist organizations cannot be expected from market participants that they will behave the same way. For example, there are certain contradictions between hotel owners, locals and tourists. In addition, interested organizations can be divided into several groups according to the interests of the hotels at the ski resort is probably beneficial reduction of one-day tourism, and the owners of the ski lifts, on the contrary, advantageous to increase the flow of tourists. Even within the same group (for example, among the hotel complexes) traced the various interests. For example, large hotels are usually less interested in offering spa services because they are all necessary for accommodation and recreational visitors at home, and smaller hotels are interested in the travel agency to offer improved resort itself organized action. An important component is relationship between travelers and locals. To reduce the difference to balance the interests of different groups can be at the expense of a balanced plan and coordinate the development of tourism with the participation of stakeholders, guided by generally accepted norms and values. External effects of tourist product can be viewed as the specifics of tourism industry.

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Today, tourism has a significant impact on areas such as economy, ecology, politics, social life, which, respectively also affect tourism. Income from tourism is involved in the local economic cycle and creates an additional (multiplier) effects. Through Tourism there provided employment, created infrastructure, construction of new objects of culture and recreation. Time Tourists create stress on infrastructure, environment, culture and recreation, which may cause dissatisfaction of local residents. If you do not take these negative effects, not to determine ways to overcome them, tourism will not be able to serve as an activator of economy. In this regard, you need to plan and build infrastructure of tourism, with participation of all interested parties and organizations. In addition, there is a certain specificity of dialogue with surrounding tourist.

Everyday life is representative of the tourist housing, work, leisure time, etc. Holidays spent in traveling - is meeting with other travel and locals. The ratio of traveler to him and his motives are determined by how people used to live, to work, it is possible that the organization of free time. As a rule, the more in everyday life one feels limited natural resources, the more it must fulfill certain norms of behavior, the greater the desire to choose to relax unknown country.

Research results indicate that behavior of the tourist impact on the attitude of local people and other travelers. So, if tourists are satisfied with noisy parties, engaged in leisure activities that adversely affect the nature, it causes a negative attitude towards them locals and can spoil the rest.

Finally, tourism management activity is specific and significantly different from the workers of other sectors, although at first it may seem that management of tourism in the region and firms is based on the same basis as management of any enterprise system "man - a man." The essential tasks of managers of tourism are:

- Determining the type of client and identifying its real needs;
- Comparison of the data from the resource potential of travel companies, is clarifying options for addressing these needs with the available tours and itineraries;
- Definition of common trends and patterns of demand, as well as its specific features.

Conclusion

Analysis of features of tourism as a control object shows that the industry is completely different from the others and therefore transferable developments and management model in other areas of labor in the sphere of tourism is impossible.

DOI

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DOI

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14. Трофимова, Т. В. (2020). Современные тенденции развития индустрии туризма в мире. In *Индустрия туризма и сервиса: состояние, проблемы, эффективность, инновации* (pp. 36-37).

